

STUDIES IN THE HYDROXYANTHRACENE SERIES. PART III.* SYNTHESIS OF SOME HETEROCYCLIC COMPOUNDS FROM 1-ANTHROL

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Syntheses of 2'-methyl- and 2'-phenyl-1:2-anthra- γ -pyrone, 2'-phenyl-2':3'-dihydro-1:2-anthra- γ -pyrone and 3-methylanthra-[1:2-b]furan have been described.

The reactions of 1-anthrol, described earlier (Lele, Shah and Sethna, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, 21, 1293), have been extended to the synthesis of anthra- γ -pyrone and anthra-furan derivatives.

2-Acetyl-1-anthrol on the Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation furnished 2'-methyl-3'-acetyl-1:2-anthra- γ -pyrone (I a). This on heating with dilute ethanolic sodium carbonate solution afforded 2'-methyl-1:2-anthra- γ -pyrone (I b), which yielded a styryl derivative with benzaldehyde, and 2-acetyl-1-anthrol on hydrolysis. The same ketone on the Kostanecki-Robinson benzoylation, gave 2'-phenyl-3'-benzoyl-1:2-anthra- γ -pyrone (I c), which on heating with dilute ethanolic sodium carbonate solution furnished 2'-phenyl-1:2-anthra- γ -pyrone (I d). The γ -pyrone derivatives (I b and I d) were also obtained by refluxing 1-anthrol with ethyl acetoacetate and ethyl benzoylacetate respectively in diphenyl ether solution according to the method of Desai *et al.* (*J. M. S. Univ., Baroda*, 1955, 4, No. 2, p. 1).

2-Acetyl-1-anthrol on condensation with benzaldehyde in presence of alkali yielded 2-hydroxyanthrylstyryl ketone. It afforded an acetyl derivative. The styryl ketone was isomerised by heating its ethanolic solution with dilute sulphuric acid to 2'-phenyl-2':3'-dihydro-1:2-anthra- γ -pyrone. This on dehydrogenation with selenium dioxide gave 2'-phenyl-1:2-anthra- γ -pyrone (I d), identified by direct comparison with the product described above.

2-Acetyl-1-anthrol on condensation with ethyl bromoacetate furnished ethyl 2-acetyl-1-anthroxacetate, which on hydrolysis gave 2-acetyl-1-anthroxacetic acid. On heating with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride it afforded 3-methylanthra-[1:2-b]furan(II). The results of analysis and the absence of a free acetyl group in this compound indicate that the meso position is not involved in the ring closure. Further, 1-anthroxacetic acid remained unchanged on subjecting it to the action of sodium acetate and acetic anhydride.

(I)

(II)

- (a) R = Me; R' = COMe.
- (b) R = Me; R' = H.
- (c) R = Ph; R' = CPh.
- (d) R = Ph; R' = H.^b

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EXPERIMENTAL*

2'-Methyl-3'-acetyl-1:2-anthra- γ -pyrone (I a).—2-Acetyl-1-anthrol (1 g.) was heated with freshly fused sodium acetate (3 g.) and acetic anhydride (6 c.c.) in an oil bath at 180° for 8 hours. The product obtained on working up the reaction mixture was crystallised from ethanol (charcoal) in light yellow needles, m.p. 196-97°. (Found : C, 79.9; H, 4.5. $C_{20}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 79.5; H, 4.6%).

2'-Methyl-1:2-anthra- γ -pyrone (I b).—The above γ -pyrone (0.5 g.) in 50% ethanol (50 c.c.) was refluxed with sodium carbonate (2 g.) for 2 hours. The product obtained was crystallised from dilute ethanol (charcoal) in yellowish brown needles, m.p. 210-11°. (Found : C, 83.5; H, 5.0. $C_{16}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 83.1; H, 4.6%). On refluxing with EtOH-KOH on a steam bath it breaks down into 2-acetyl-1-anthrol.

The same product was obtained when 1-anthrol (0.99 g.) in hot diphenyl ether was refluxed for 2 hours with ethyl acetoacetate (0.65 g.) and the solution diluted on cooling with petroleum ether.

2'-Styryl-2:1-anthra- γ -pyrone.—The above γ -pyrone (0.1 g.) was dissolved in ethanol (5 c.c.) and treated successively with benzaldehyde (0.1 g.) and a solution of sodium ethoxide (prepared from 0.1 g. of sodium). The greenish yellow crystalline product, which separated on keeping overnight, was filtered and recrystallised from dilute ethanol (charcoal) in yellow shining needles, m.p. 216°. (Found : C, 85.8; H, 4.6. $C_{25}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 86.2; H, 4.6%).

2'-Phenyl-3'-benzoyl-1-anthra- γ -pyrone (I c).—2-Acetyl-1-anthrol (1 g.) was heated with freshly fused sodium benzoate (1.5 g.) and benzoic anhydride (5 g.) in an oil bath at 180° for 8 hours. The reaction mixture was then treated repeatedly with hot water and sodium bicarbonate, and the residue was crystallised from ethanol (charcoal) in small yellow needles, m.p. 222 (Found : C, 84.4; H, 4.1. $C_{30}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 84.5; H, 4.2%).

2'-Phenyl-1:2-anthra- γ -pyrone (I d).—The above γ -pyrone (0.5 g.) in 50% ethanol (50 c.c.) was refluxed with sodium carbonate (2 g.) for 2 hours. The product obtained was crystallised from ethanol (charcoal) in yellow needles, m.p. 215-16°. (Found : C, 85.8; H, 4.6. $C_{23}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 85.7; H, 4.4%).

The same product was obtained when 1-anthrol (0.48 g.) in hot diphenyl ether was refluxed for 2 hours with ethyl benzoylacetate (0.48 g.); the solution on cooling was diluted with petroleum ether.

2-Hydroxyanthrylstyryl Ketone.—To a mixture of 2-acetyl 1-anthrol (1.2 g.) and benzaldehyde (2. c.c.) in ethanol (50 c.c.) KOH solution (2.5 g. in 5 c.c. water) was added in small lots. The air was removed by bubbling nitrogen through the solution; the flask was corked and kept for 2 days at room temperature. The product separating on dilution of the reaction mixture was crystallised from ethanol in reddish brown needles, m.p. 207°. (Found : C, 84.8; H, 4.8. $C_{23}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 85.2; H, 4.9%). It develops a reddish brown coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The *acetyl derivative* was prepared by heating the styryl ketone (0.1 g.) with acetic anhydride (1 c.c.) and freshly fused sodium acetate (0.1 g.) on a steam bath for 5 hours. It was crystallised from ethanol (charcoal) in small yellowish needles, m.p. 180-81°. (Found : C, 82.3; H, 5.2. $C_{25}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 82.0; H, 4.9%).

All melting points are uncorrected.

2'-Phenyl-2' : 3'-dihydro-1 : 2-anthra- γ -pyrone.—The above hydroxyanthrylstyryl ketone (0.1 g.) in ethanol (100 c.c.) was refluxed on a steam bath for 48 hours with 10% H_2SO_4 (10 c.c.). The product separating on dilution with water was crystallised from chloroform, m.p. 231°. (Found : C, 84.8 ; H, 4.8. $C_{23}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 85.2 ; H, 4.9%).

A mixture of this substance (0.1 g.), selenium dioxide (0.2 g.), and amyl alcohol (10 c.c.) was heated under reflux at 150° for 8 hours ; the reaction mixture was then filtered hot. On evaporation of the amyl alcohol the product obtained was crystallised from ethanol in light yellow needles ; m.p. and mixed m.p. with 2'-phenyl-1 : 2-anthra- γ -pyrone was 215-16°.

Ethyl 2-Acetyl-1-anthroxyacetate.—A mixture of 2-acetyl-1-anthrol (0.5 g.), ethyl bromoacetate (0.5 c.c.), and anhydrous potassium carbonate (3 g.) was refluxed in acetone solution for 4 hours. The product obtained on removal of acetone was crystallised from dilute ethanol (charcoal) in golden yellow needles, m.p. 108-109°. (Found : C, 74.9 ; H, 5.3. $C_{20}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 74.5 ; H, 5.6%).

2-Acetyl-1-anthroxyacetic Acid.—The above ester (0.5 g.) was heated with 2% NaOH solution (50 c.c.) at 50° in a water bath till the ester dissolved. The solution was then filtered hot. The product obtained on acidification of the filtrate was crystallised from dilute acetic acid (charcoal) in yellow needles, m.p. 161-62° (efferv.). (Found : C, 73.1 ; H, 4.5. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 73.5 ; H, 4.8%).

3-Methylanthra-(1 : 2-b)furan (II).—A mixture of the above acid (0.1 g.), acetic anhydride (2 c.c.), and freshly fused sodium acetate (0.3 g.) was refluxed for 30 minutes. The product obtained on pouring it in water was crystallised from ethanol (charcoal) in light yellow needles, m.p. 104°. (Found : C, 87.3 ; H, 5.6. $C_{17}H_{12}O$ requires C, 87.9 ; H, 5.2%).

1-Anthroxyacetic Acid.—A mixture of 1-anthrol (1 g.), ethyl bromoacetate (1 c.c.), and anhydrous potassium carbonate (3 g.) was refluxed in acetone solution for 7 hours. An oil was obtained on removal of acetone. This was hydrolysed in ethanolic solution with KOH (2 g. in 5 c.c. water) by heating on a steam bath for 2 hours. The product obtained was purified through sodium bicarbonate treatment and crystallised first from dilute ethanol (charcoal) and then from benzene in colorless needles, m.p. 190-91°. (Found : C, 76.3 ; H, 4.9. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 76.2 ; H, 4.8%).

The acid (0.1 g.) was refluxed with sodium acetate (0.3 g.) and acetic anhydride (2 c.c.) for 30 minutes. The original acid was obtained on working up the reaction mixture.